

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

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Deliverable D5.1: UNITI's Ensemble-based Prediction Models

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1 Introduction

The overall aim of the UNITI project is to develop a decision support system (DSS) to address the question which treatment approach is optimal for a specific patient. Clinical, epidemiological, medical, genetic and audiological data, including signals reflecting ear-brain communication, shall be analyzed by computational models to extract those factors that are of prognostic relevance.

An important step towards this goal is to build ensemble mechanisms that combine the computational models derived from the clinic-specific data and develop a voting scheme that takes into account the distribution of the phenotypes and allows to predict the medical outcome as well as the adherence to the clinical intervention.

This deliverable will report on the currently developed data models on phenotypes, predictors and adherence which are the basis for the voting scheme. A large variety of data models has been applied and compared.

Overall, there are already six published papers from the UNITI group on this topic which are listed in the references. Two more articles are currently under review. An overview is presented in the following chapters. A conceptual paper on the UNITI DSS with an analysis on the requirements for the DSS, requirements for the underlying data base, requirements for the underlying knowledge base and requirements for the algorithms was published earlier this year in the manuscript Schlee et al. 2021.

2 Modelling tinnitus phenotypes

In this chapter we will present five scientific publications that applied different computational models to better characterize and understand tinnitus patient subgroups, adherence to treatment and predict the outcome of the clinical intervention.

In the work by Niemann and colleagues (Niemann et al., 2020a) a cluster analysis approach was used to identify distinct tinnitus phenotypes. A database with 1'228 chronic tinnitus patients with self-reported questionnaire data was used for the analysis. The questionnaires assessed tinnitus distress, tinnitus loudness, tinnitus frequency, tinnitus location, depression, perceived stress, quality of life, physical and mental health, pain perception, somatic symptoms and coping attitudes. The cluster algorithm identified four patient groups which were named “avoidant group” (56.8%), “psychosomatic group” (14.1%), “somatic group” (15.2%), and “distress group” (13.9%). The figures 2.1 and 2.2 have been produced for visual inspection of the patient characteristics.

Figure 2.1 Visualization of the four patient subgroups. (published in Niemann et al. 2020a).

Figure 2.2 Comparison of the four patient subgroups with respect to major phenotype characteristics. (published in Niemann et al. 2020a).

In another publication by the same group (Niemann et al., 2020b), eleven different computational models were applied and compared to each other. These machine learning algorithms were trained to classify patient groups based on 185 variables from self-reported questionnaires. A 10-fold cross-validation scheme to ensure robust and predictive classifiers. The analysis was based on a data set of 1'490 chronic tinnitus patients that completed a 7-days multimodal treatment including cognitive behavioral treatment, structured counselling, and physiotherapy. The models were trained to predict the outcome of the clinical intervention. A comparison of the eleven computational models is shown in table 2.1. The best trade-off between high predictive performance ($AUC = 0.85 \pm 0.05$) and a low number of features ($n = 6$) was found for the LASSO model. The phenotype features with the strongest coefficients are shown in table 2.2.

Classification method											
<i>i</i>	lasso	ridge	wknn	nb	svm	gpls	nnet	cart	c5.0	rf	gbt
1	0.867 (185)	0.864 (185)	0.853 (185)	0.852 (185)	0.851 (185)	0.838 (185)	0.822 (185)	0.795 (185)	0.795 (185)	0.864 (185)	0.862 (185)
2	0.856 (89)	0.847 (86)	0.845 (98)	0.849 (70)	0.530 (5)	0.836 (80)	0.807 (117)	0.799 (106)	0.803 (103)	0.864 (109)	0.855 (89)
3	0.857 (50)	0.854 (51)	0.845 (65)	0.829 (38)	0.537 (4)	0.836 (47)	0.809 (87)	0.794 (66)	0.803 (62)	0.866 (99)	0.859 (52)
4	0.856 (24)	0.853 (31)	0.837 (40)	0.832 (26)	0.542 (3)	0.838 (24)	0.801 (59)	0.799 (45)	0.790 (39)	0.865 (85)	0.858 (38)
5	0.853 (17)	0.853 (21)	0.842 (28)	0.838 (15)	0.562 (2)	0.838 (16)	0.793 (45)	0.811 (34)	0.806 (24)	0.865 (77)	0.855 (24)
6	0.854 (10)	0.851 (15)	0.847 (16)	0.841 (13)	—	0.837 (9)	0.810 (25)	0.817 (28)	0.803 (23)	0.863 (75)	0.856 (16)
7	0.850 (6)	0.854 (11)	0.833 (9)	—	—	0.838 (6)	0.812 (21)	0.822 (24)	0.804 (16)	0.864 (69)	0.854 (14)
8	—	0.854 (9)	0.829 (7)	—	—	—	0.852 (12)	0.822 (23)	0.802 (13)	0.865 (64)	0.853 (11)
9	—	0.854 (8)	0.830 (6)	—	—	—	0.857 (8)	0.822 (22)	0.802 (12)	0.865 (59)	—
10	—	0.853 (7)	—	—	—	—	0.842 (4)	—	0.809 (10)	0.866 (57)	—
11	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.865 (56)	—
12	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.864 (51)	—
13	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.864 (50)	—
14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.863 (47)	—

Table 2.1 Comparison of the eleven computational models. Classification performance is reported by the mean cross-validation AUC and the number of used features is reported in parenthesis (published in Niemann et al. 2020b).

Feature	Description	Coefficient
SOZK_nationality	German nationality	-0.370
ADSL_adsl06	“During the past week I felt depressed”.	0.309
ADSL_adsl19	“During the past week I felt that people disliked me”.	0.288
PSQ_stress21	“You enjoy yourself”.	-0.284
SOZK_graduate	Graduation: university	-0.210
ADSL_adsl11	“During the past week my sleep was restless”.	0.196
ADSL_adsl03	“During the past week I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with help from my family or friends”.	0.175
TQ_tin50	Because of the noises I am unable to enjoy the radio or television.	0.151
TQ_tin47	I am a victim of my noises.	0.137
ADSL_adsl02	“During the past week I did not feel like eating; my appetite was poor”.	0.132
ADSL_adsl05	“During the past week I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing”.	0.132
SF8_sf07	“During the past 4 weeks, how much have you been bothered by emotional problems (such as feeling anxious, depressed or irritable)?”	0.125
ADSL_adsl10	“During the past week I felt fearful”.	0.107
ADSL_adsl04	“During the past week I felt I was just as good as other people”.	-0.107
TQ_tin40	I am able to forget about the noises when I am doing something interesting.	-0.104
ADSL_adsl16	“During the past week I enjoyed life”.	-0.085
PSQ_stress15	“Your problems seem to be piling up”.	0.081
TQ_tin07	Most of the time the noises are fairly quiet.	-0.069
ADSL_adsl08	“During the past week I felt hopeful about the future”.	-0.064
SF8_sf02	“During the past 4 weeks, how much did physical health problems limit your physical activities (such as walking or climbing stairs)?”	0.059
SOZK_tinnitusdur	“How long have you been suffering from tinnitus (in years)?”	0.058
PSQ_stress28	“You feel loaded down with responsibility”.	0.055
ADSL_adsl18	“During the past week I felt sad”.	0.053
SOZK_job	Job status: currently employed	-0.050
ADSL_adsl13	“During the past week I talked less than usual”.	0.049

Table 2.2 Most important phenotype features. The 25 phenotype features with the highest absolute coefficients in the LASSO model are shown (published in Niemann et al. 2020b).

In the publication by Niemann and colleagues (Niemann et al. 2020c), the authors concentrated on the influence of gender. For the computational modelling, we developed a workflow that comprises machine learning, comprehensive evaluation including hyperparameter optimization and post-learning to identify predictive variables. Five different machine learning approaches were compared and a 10-fold cross-validation applied. The analysis was based on a dataset of 1'628 chronic tinnitus patients with 828 female patients and 800 male patients. The results showed fundamental gender differences in the reported symptoms and treatment responses, e.g. female patients report higher levels of tension, stress and psychological coping strategies while male patients report higher levels of tinnitus-associated pain and judge their overall health as better. Also, the contribution of phenotype characteristics to the computational models differed, which highlights that gender is an important factor to be modeled within the UNITI decision support system. Figure 2.3 gives an overview of the performance of the classification results and computational models.

LT	Target	Target distribution	Method	Accuracy [%]	Sens. ♀[%]	Sens. ♂[%]
1	Gender		RIDGE	72.19±2.94*	71.41±5.46	73.02±4.30
			SVM	71.82 ± 3.66*	70.93 ± 5.17	72.70 ± 6.00
			LASSO	71.33 ± 3.03*	69.49 ± 4.23	73.19 ± 4.88
			GBT	70.35 ± 3.36*	70.91 ± 5.05	69.72 ± 6.20
			RF	68.63 ± 5.24*	68.67 ± 5.95	68.58 ± 7.14
LT	Subset	Target	Target distribution	Method	RMSE	R ²
2a	only ♀	TQ_distress (T0)		GBT	10.92±0.68*	0.55±0.04
				RF	11.38±0.74*	0.51±0.05
				LASSO	11.55±0.70*	0.50±0.04
				RIDGE	11.59±0.63*	0.50±0.04
				SVM	11.97±0.51*	0.46±0.03
2b	only ♂	TQ_distress (T0)		GBT	10.11±1.12*	0.68±0.06
				RF	10.58±1.01*	0.65±0.06
				LASSO	10.59±0.98*	0.65±0.05
				RIDGE	10.72±1.05*	0.64±0.06
				SVM	11.21±1.02*	0.61±0.06
3a	only ♀	ADSL_depression (T0)		LASSO	5.80±0.73*	0.74±0.06
				GBT	5.88±0.65*	0.74±0.06
				RF	6.02±0.62*	0.72±0.05
				GBT	6.10±0.65*	0.72±0.06
				SVM	6.12±0.72*	0.71±0.06
3b	only ♂	ADSL_depression (T0)		LASSO	5.10±0.38*	0.81±0.03
				RIDGE	5.14±0.38*	0.80±0.03
				GBT	5.16±0.42*	0.80±0.04
				SVM	5.29±0.38*	0.79±0.03
				RF	5.29±0.46*	0.79±0.04
4a	only ♀	Treatment effect TQ_distress (T0 → T1)		RF	9.55±0.84	0.02±0.09
				RIDGE	9.58±0.82	0.01±0.09
				GBT	9.59±0.82	0.01±0.08
				LASSO	9.61±0.82	0.01±0.08
				SVM	9.64±0.83	0.00±0.09
4b	only ♂	Treatment effect TQ_distress (T0 → T1)		RF	9.34±1.31	0.04±0.14
				LASSO	9.41±1.34	0.03±0.14
				RIDGE	9.43±1.31	0.03±0.14
				GBT	9.54±1.32	0.00±0.14
				SVM	9.55±1.36	0.00±0.14
5a	only ♀	Treatment effect ADSL_depression (T0 → T1)		LASSO	8.21±0.77	0.14±0.09
				RIDGE	8.21±0.80	0.14±0.09
				RF	8.23±0.73	0.13±0.08
				SVM	8.26±0.84	0.13±0.10
				GBT	8.26±0.77	0.13±0.09
5b	only ♂	Treatment effect ADSL_depression (T0 → T1)		GBT	6.79±0.73	0.17±0.10
				RF	6.82±0.68	0.16±0.09
				RIDGE	6.84±0.73	0.16±0.10
				LASSO	6.85±0.71	0.15±0.10
				SVM	7.15±0.64	0.08±0.09

Figure 2.3 Comparison of the computational models and overview of the gender-specific classification results (published in Niemann et al. 2020c).

Besides the clinical data, we are also using Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) data to investigate the development of clinical symptoms over time. Schleicher and colleagues (Schleicher et al. 2020) used a data set of an earlier EMA project, called TrackYourTinnitus,

to apply computational modelling on time series data. Seven different algorithms were applied on a dataset of 1'292 users with tinnitus. The TrackYourTinnitus project is an open study where users can participate by downloading a smartphone app and registering. The user can start, stop and re-start at any time. The computational algorithms were used to model how long the participants used the EMA app, if they return to the EMA app after a longer break and which patient characteristics are related to it. An overview of the applied computational models and their prediction improvement depended on item and sampling time point is given in Table 2.3. The results showed that patients that are concerned about their physical health, patients that have difficulties with sleep, and patients that are disturbed by the tinnitus loudness, are more likely to continue app usage after a break. For modeling EMA data, compared to clinical questionnaire data (e.g. in the studies by Niemann et al. 2020 a,b,c) it is important to also model the time point of the data sampling as the prediction improvements of the items seem to change in time.

Algorithm	EMA item	FirstDays			
		2	3	4	≥ 10
ST	q1	–	0.71	×	×
	q5	–	×	0.83	×
	q6	–	0.68	×	×
TSF	q1	0.61	×	×	×
	q5	0.61	0.69	×	×
EE	q5	0.66	×	×	×
MSM	q5	0.63	×	×	×
CID _{DTW}	q1	0.61	×	×	×
	q5	0.63	×	×	×
DTD _C	q1	0.62	×	0.78	×
	q2	×	×	×	0.67
	q5	0.61	×	×	×
DD _{DTW}	q1	0.61	×	×	×
	q5	0.61	×	×	×
DTW	q2	×	×	×	0.67
	q5	0.63	×	×	×
RotF	q1	×	0.71	×	×
	q5	×	0.69	×	×
NB	q4	×	×	×	0.66
	q5	×	0.69	×	×
	q7	×	0.71	×	×
ED	q1	0.62	×	0.78	×
	q2	×	×	×	0.67
	q5	0.63	×	×	×

Table 2.3 Comparison of computational models using the TrackYourTinnitus EMA data set. Models with a significant improvement of accuracy are shown, in dependence of EMA item and sampling time point (published in Schleicher et al. 2020).

In another EMA data set, Unnikrishnan and colleagues (Unnikrishnan et al., 2020) compared an approach using cluster-level models and compared it to a single global model. An EMA data set with 5'719 EMA recordings was used. The data was collected within a smartphone-based study where the patients received self-help tips for dealing with their tinnitus, combined with a tinnitus diary that consists of similar questions like the Schleicher et al. 2020. Three different patient groups were investigated that received different schedules of tips and diary samplings. Computational models were used to predict today's tinnitus distress of the individual patient given today's tinnitus loudness. A cluster-model approach with five patient clusters was compared to a single global computational model. Results showed that cluster-level model outperformed the single model. Figure 2.4 shows the root mean square error for the global model ("all") and the individual clusters. Given the large heterogeneity of the tinnitus patient population that consists of a (yet unknown) number of patient subgroups, this explains the advantage of the cluster-model approach over the single global model. Therefore, cluster models need to be taken into account for the computational models for the UNITI DSS.

Figure 2.4 Root mean square error for the single global model ("all") and the clusters of the cluster-model showing an advantage for the cluster-model approach (published in Unnikrishnan et al. 2020).

3 Voting Scheme

With our current work in this work package, we consider a large variety of algorithms for computational modelling, apply them to already existing tinnitus data sets and systematically evaluate the applicability and efficacy of the models in the field of tinnitus. In principle there are two ways to use these computational models for the final UNITI decision support system: The first option is to choose the best model and implement it in the DSS. The second option is to select all models that perform better than a threshold and combine them into an *ensemble*. This ensemble is then implemented in the clinical Decision Support System. Within such an ensemble:

- each ensemble member, i.e. each individual model, makes a prediction for the outcome after treatment for each patient
- and associates a weight with this prediction; this weight reflects the confidence of the predictor to its prediction
- and casts a vote on the predicted outcome; the vote can be weighted with the confidence of the predictor.

The final prediction of the outcome is cast by a weighted majority voting of all ensemble members.

In our analysis of mHealth data (Schleicher et al, 2020) we have used an off-the-shelf ensemble learner in the form of a Random Forest (RF). The RF ensemble members exploit different areas of the data space and different subspaces of the feature space during learning, but they constitute a blackbox of many weak classifiers that only delivers satisfactory quality when used as a whole. Moreover, in UNITI we want to align well to the heterogeneity of tinnitus patients, as is already reflected in phenotypes we have earlier identified. Therefore, for the UNITI decision support system we anticipate a smaller ensemble with equally lightweight but more powerful members that exploit local features of the data space for predicting the treatment response of different patient subgroups. The algorithms that have been developed for the already existing data (as used in the papers described above) will be applied on the highly standardized data of the UNITI Randomized Clinical Trial after the trial is completed.

4 Conclusion

The ultimate aim of the UNITI project is to develop a clinical Decision Support System for guiding the treatment decision for the different tinnitus subgroups. For reaching this goal, we need large-scale standardized data from clinical trials as well as the computational models that allow a high-quality prediction of the clinical outcome. With the UNITI Randomized Clinical Trial, we are currently collecting the data set. This RCT has just started. With the work presented in this deliverable, we are developing and testing the algorithms for modeling the treatment outcome. In this step, we are applying the algorithms on already existing data sets of the UNITI clinical centers. With this work we are 1) gaining new scientific knowledge about the tinnitus and about the most important predictors for treatment success, 2) learning about the differences between the specialized clinical centers within UNITI, 3) learning about the difference in computational modeling of clinical data and EMA data and 4) developing our algorithms for the computational model needed in the UNITI DSS. A large number of scientific papers towards this goal has already been finished and published. Several more papers are currently under review or in preparation.

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